

BIOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF IRRITABLE BOWEL SYNDROME IN PUBLIC AGE SCHOOL STUDENTS EARLY DIAGNOSIS WITH HELP

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Abstract: Irritable bowel syndrome is a serious and underestimated problem in childhood. This the topic is not well studied in pediatrics compared to adult practice, and pediatricians often make this diagnosis in young children without proper justification. In the thesis early diagnosis of irritable bowel syndrome in adolescent schoolchildren using biochemical analyzes is talked about.

Keywords: IBS, functional bowel disorders, biochemical analysis, children, school, adulthood.

Purpose of work. Bdevelopment of a method for differentiating irritable bowel syndrome in school children using blood biochemical analyses.

Materials and methods. A questionnaire survey was conducted among schoolchildren in 4 districts and the city of Bukhara. 1016 adult schoolchildren participated in the survey, of which girls are slightly more than boys - 571 (56.2%) - 445 (43.8%). The age structure consists of 433 (42.6%) children aged 12-13, 405 (39.8%) aged 14-15 and 178 (17.6%) aged 16-17. The study of biochemical indicators of blood in adolescents with IBS showed an increase in liver transferases:

- significant increase of ALT in adolescents of groups 2 and 3 to 39.4 ± 1.27 mmol/l and 30.1 ± 1.1 mmol/l, respectively, compared to the control values of 25.4 ± 0.64 mmol/l increase is observed ($p < 0.05$).);
- AST increased to 62.1 ± 1.67 mmol/l only in group 2 teenagers.

Fisher's exact score showed the reliability of studying ALT and AST in IBS in adolescents: $R^2 = 0.8121$ and $R^2 \setminus u003d 0.7801$. Therefore, in adolescents with a combination of respiratory allergy and IBS, an increase in liver transaminases is characteristic, which indicates the involvement of the liver in the pathological process and the development of inflammation or liver tissue damage. In non-allergic IBS, there is also a tendency for hyperalanine aminotransferase, which should be taken into account in making a correct diagnosis in adolescents.

Summary. For the differential diagnosis of reactive hepatitis and other diseases of the liver and gallbladder, analyzes were performed to determine the level of total bilirubin with direct and indirect fractions. As a result, we obtained

information indicating a relative imbalance in bilirubin metabolism in adolescents with IBS:

- a tendency to increase the level of total bilirubin and its direct fraction combined with IBS PA and without allergy - 12.6 ± 1.08 mmol/l and 5.0 ± 0.52 mmol/l, 12 It was determined up to 2 ± 0.9 mmol. /l and 2.8 ± 0.1 mmol/l, compared to healthy teenagers - 9.5 ± 0.28 mmol/l and 2.5 ± 0.08 mmol/l, $R < 0.05$

- an imbalance in the composition of indirect fractions of bilirubin was detected, the indirect fraction of bilirubin was previously noted in adolescents with IBS not associated with allergies, that is, in adolescents of group $3.9.4 \pm 0.82$ mmol/l - 7.0 ± 0.23 mmol/l compared to control, which is statistically significant at the $p < 0.05$ level.

The obtained results show that the liver tissue is involved in the pathological process, which is important for the differential diagnosis of IBS in adolescents.

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